

Applications of Refractive Index in Chemical Constitution : Refractive Index and Boiling Point Relation

D. P. Joshi

A new constant, refractive index-boiling point relation, R_T , additive and constitutive, given by

$$R_T = \frac{M \cdot n}{d} \ln T_b,$$

[M is the molecular weight, n , the refractive index for D -line at 20° , d , the density (d_4^{20}), and T_b , absolute boiling point] has been suggested. The atomic, group, and structural values of this constant have been evaluated and it has been shown to be useful in the study of structural problems, association and study of mixtures of two components.

Physical properties as surface tension and refractive index were used in expressions as parachor [P] or molar refraction R_L , which are forms of molar volume for the study of various types of chemical problems. But it has been noticed that the difference in the value of [P] or R_L of isomeric compounds or groups and between the observed and calculated values in associated liquids is usually small and these have thus limited applications in this direction. Boiling point has also been utilised for structural studies and various expressions using it have been suggested from time to time. Nakrassow¹ suggested a formula

$$\frac{T_b \cdot R_L^{\frac{1}{2}}}{M - R_L} = \text{const.} \simeq 32.7,$$

where R_L is molar refraction:

$$\left(R_L = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{d} \right)$$

(where M is the molecular weight and T_b is the boiling point) with the idea of securing better information on structural problems.

Physical constants, which could show a larger difference in classes of compounds cited above, shall have utility in distinguishing them or in similar other chemical problems and as such may serve some useful purpose. With this object in view an expression:

$$R_T = \frac{M \cdot n}{d} \ln T_b$$

(where M is the molecular weight; n is refractive index; d is density; T_b is the absolute boiling point at a constant pressure, and R_T is a constant; for finding out the atomic, group or structural values n_D^{20} , d_4^{20} and T_b at 760 mm pressure have been taken) is suggested. As

1. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, 140, 342; 1929, 141, 378.

a result of the study of a large number of normal compounds, the values of the constant R_T have been found to be additive and constitutive. Some of the atomic, structural, and group values of this constant have been derived and recorded in Table I. The procedure adopted by A. I. Vogel and coworkers and their data of n_D^{20} , d_4^{20} , molecular weight², except for octyl³ alcohol from Mumford and Phillips³, have been used. The boiling points at 760 mm pressure have been used and, where it is given otherwise, have mostly been taken from three collective works⁴.

TABLE I

Atomic, structural, and group values of R_T .

Atom, structure, or group.	R_T .	Atom, structure, or group.	R_T .
CH ₂	.. 30.01	C ₄ H ₉ ^{sec} (sec-butyl group)	.. 129.87
C(in CH ₂)	.. 12.19	I (aliphatic)	.. 65.49
H (in CH ₂)	.. 8.01	I (aromatic)	.. 68.59
O (in ethers & acetals)	.. 11.69	OH (in aliphatic alcohols)	.. 13.24
CO (in methylketones)	.. 28.49	NH ₂ (in primary aliphatic amines)	.. 23.57
CO (in other ketones)	.. 26.89	NH ₂ (in primary aromatic amines)	.. 26.62
CO ₂ (in esters)	.. 40.43	NH (in secondary aliphatic amines)	.. 18.84
CO ₂ H	.. 48.13	NH (in secondary aromatic amines)	.. 19.61
F (aliphatic)	.. 10.47	N (in tertiary aliphatic amines)	.. 11.13
F (aromatic)	.. 12.24	N (in tertiary aromatic amines)	.. 10.38
Cl (aliphatic)	.. 33.18	S (in aliphatic sulphides)	.. 35.29
Cl (aromatic)	.. 35.71	S (in aromatic sulphides)	.. 37.11
Br (aliphatic)	.. 44.29	S ₂ (in aliphatic disulphides)	.. 74.63
Br (aromatic)	.. 47.17	SH (in thiols aliphatic)	.. 43.87
NO (nitroso aliphatic)	.. 31.77	SH (in thiols aromatic)	.. 46.86
NO (nitroso aromatic)	.. 33.77	SCN (in thiocyanates)	.. 74.55
ONO (nitrite aliphatic)	.. 48.18	NCS (in isothiocyanates)	.. 79.67
NO ₂ (nitro aliphatic)	.. 42.54	C-C double bond	.. 9.66
NO ₂ (nitro aromatic)	.. 44.77	C-C triple bond	.. 14.71
N.NO (in nitrosoamine)	.. 42.18	C.C three-membered ring	.. 1.58
NO ₃	.. 57.36	C.C four-membered ring	.. -0.69
SO ₃	.. 69.11	C.C five-membered ring	.. -5.60
CO ₃	.. 51.77	C.C six-membered ring	.. -8.25
SO ₄	.. 75.72	Methyl group	.. 38.63
PO ₄	.. 70.79	Phenyl group	.. 140.29
C ₃ H ₇ ^{is} (isopropyl group)	.. 100.81	C ₃ H ₅ (allyl group)	.. 91.80
C ₄ H ₉ ^{is} (isobutyl group)	.. 128.88	C ₄ H ₉ ^{tert} (tert-butyl group)	.. 132.50

2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1323; 1940, 174; 1943, 636; 1946, 133; 1948, 607, 610, 624, 654, 658, 1809, 1814, 1825, 1833.

3. *Ibid.*, 1950, 76.

4. (i) International Critical Tables, McGraw Hills Book Co., New York, 1926, Vol. I, pp. 176-275; (ii) F. Beilstein, "Handbook der organischen Chemie, Julius Springer, Berlin, Vol. I (1918), 574, 603, 709, 123, 133, 147; Vol. I (Erstes—1929), 301, 365, 370; Vol. II (1920), 611, 776, 852; Vol. V (1922) 5, 63, 108; Vol. V (Erstes—1930), 211; Vol. VI (1923) 6; Vol. VI (Zwites—1944); 3; Vol. VI (Erstes—1931), 82; Vol. VII (1925), 407; Vol. IX (1926), 511 and (iii) J. Timmermann, "Physico Chemical Constants of Pure Organic Compounds", Elsevier, 1950, pp. 151, 157, 159.

As shown below, the difference in R_T values of isomeric compounds and groups being larger, the constant can prove more useful in distinguishing them from one another.

Structural Study.—The isomeric compounds and groups, in which the linking of multivalent atoms is different, show a larger difference with R_T values than in the case of $[P]$ or R_D . Some of these are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Compound or group.	R_T (diff.).	R_D (diff.).	$[P]$ (diff.)
1. Nitrite Nitro	5.64	0.524	1.50
2. Isothiocyanat Thiocyanate	5.00	2.250	1.90
3. <i>o</i> -Xylene <i>m</i> - " " <i>p</i> - " "	1.78 0.61	0.085 0.058	0.96 0.00
4. <i>o</i> -Ethyltoluene <i>m</i> - " " <i>p</i> - " "	3.23 0.68	0.252 0.006	

Again in the case of other structural problems, R_T values may give useful information. Thus in the case of dicyclohexyl, the R_T values of the two six-membered rings joined by a bond is -2×8.5 , whereas the value of the two condensed six-membered rings (from α -naphthalene derivaives) is -4.48. The $[P]$ values for both of these are the same.

Association.—In the case of associated liquids, e.g., lower alcohols, lower primary amines, acetic acid, etc., the difference between the observed and calculated values of R_T are quite appreciable. Thus for methanol, propylⁿ amine, and acetic acid, the observed R_T values are 58.44, 124.56, and 89.02 respectively, whereas their calculated values are respectively 51.87, 122.22, and 87.76. Such large difference is not shown in the case of R_D values and can be utilised for finding the extent of association.

R_T Values in Mixture Law.—The straight line mixture law has been tried in two-component systems (both the component being liquids);

$$R_T(m) = f \cdot R_{T(x)} + (1-f) R_{T(s)}$$

where $R_{T(m)}$ is the value observed for the mixture, $R_{T(s)}$ for the component taken as solvent, and $R_{T(x)}$, the other component taken as solute. The value of $R_{T(s)}$ is given under the 5th column [$R_{T(m)}$ obs.] in parenthesis, f is the mol. fraction of the solute given in column 1. The results show good agreement in the case of the first three mixtures (I to III) between the value of $R_{T(x)}$ from the mixture and the observed and also with the calculated from the atomic, group, and structural values (however, the atomic group and structural values used are at 760 mm pressure and the experimental values, a little away from it). In the case of mixtures IV, V, and VI, the dilution effect has been observed. For the *m*-cresol (IV) and aniline (V), the $R_{T(x)}$ value from the mixture approaches the observed value with increasing concentration, whereas in the mixture of chlorobenzene in nitrobenzene (VI), the $R_{T(x)}$ value from mixture approaches the observed value in dilute solution and falls off as the concentration is increased.

TABLE III

I. Nitrobenzene in aniline (pressure 74.00 cm).

M.f.	n_D^{20}	d_4^{20}	B.P.	$R_T(m)$ obs.	$R_T(x)$ from mix.
0	1.5853	1.0244	182.8°	(166.75)	..
0.08381	1.5803	1.0359	183.6°	168.36	185.96
0.44012	1.5683	1.1032	190.0°	174.82	185.23
0.53797	1.5653	1.1203	192.7°	176.87	185.56
1.00000	1.5530	1.2035	208.0°	..	185.10

Mean $R_T(x)$ from mix. = 185.58; $R_T(x)$ obs. = 185.10; $R_T(x)$ calc. = 185.06.

II. Chlorobenzene in aniline (pressure 74.00 cm).

0	1.5853	1.0244	182.8°	(166.75)	..
0.11230	1.5751	1.0310	176.3°	167.58	174.24
0.39839	1.5590	1.0523	158.3°	170.48	176.36
0.84608	1.5330	1.0924	137.8°	174.44	175.83
1.0000	1.5251	1.1062	131.0°	..	175.37

Mean $R_T(x)$ from mix. = 175.48; $R_T(x)$ obs. = 175.37; $R_T(x)$ calc. = 176.00.

III. Bromobenzene in benzene (pressure 74.04 cm).

0	1.5015	0.8900	79.2°	(147.36)	..
0.07561	1.5078	0.9301	79.6°	150.76	192.15*
0.57432	1.5399	1.2553	112.4°	170.04	186.71
0.87787	1.5550	1.4289	151.0°	183.00	187.96
1.0000	1.5601	1.4967	155.4°	..	187.07

Mean $R_T(x)$ from mix. = 187.33 (except*); $R_T(x)$ obs. = 187.07; $R_T(x)$ calc. = 187.46.

IV. *m*-Cresol in benzene (pressure 74.12 cm).

0	1.5011	0.8789	79.3°	(147.39)	..
0.04448	1.5029	0.8965	79.7°	149.01	184.21
0.16286	1.5090	0.9073	87.0°	153.41	184.32
0.62431	1.5288	0.9613	143.3°	170.94	185.10
1.0000	1.5389	1.0348	202.0°	..	186.90

Mean $R_T(x)$ from mix. = 184.54; $R_T(x)$ obs. = 186.90; $R_T(x)$ calc. =

V. Aniline in benzene (pressure 74.00 cm.).

0	1.5011	0.8789	79.2°	(147.39)	..
0.01388	1.5025	0.8903	79.4°	147.86	159.88*
0.33834	1.5382	0.9285	92.0°	153.37	165.06
0.86555	1.5772	1.0047	172.0°	164.52	167.19
1.0000	1.5863	1.0244	182.8°	..	166.75

Mean $R_T(x)$ from mix. = 166.13 (except*); $R_T(x)$ obs. = 166.75; $R_T(x)$ calc. = 166.91.

VI. Chlorobenzene in nitrobenzene (pressure 74.00 cm).

0	1.5530	1.2035	208.0°	(185.10)	..
0.16090	1.5481	1.1877	191.5°	183.32	174.08
0.48823	1.5390	1.1561	161.9°	179.23	173.08
0.86186	1.5282	1.1179	139.1°	173.85	172.23
1.0000	1.5251	1.1062	131.0°	..	175.57

Mean $R_T(x)$ from mix. = 173.17; $R_T(x)$ obs. = 175.57; $R_T(x)$ calc. = 176.00.

R_T values have been applied to some liquid mixtures below, in which refractive index and density data are due to Williams and Krachma⁵, and the boiling point from "International Critical Tables"⁶. There is good agreement between the observed and calculated values.

TABLE IV

I. CCl ₄ in benzene.			II. CCl ₄ in toluene.		
M.f.	$R_{T(m)}$ obs.	$R_{T(x)}$ from mix.	M.f.	$R_{T(m)}$ obs.	$R_{T(x)}$ from mix.
1.00	..	156.38	1.00	..	156.38
0.75	154.50	156.57	0.50	167.52	157.61
0.50	152.49	156.70	0.00	(179.71)	..
0.00	(148.28)	..			
III. CCl ₄ in chloroform.			IV. CCl ₄ in EtOH.		
1.00	..	156.38	1.00	..	156.32
0.50	141.00	155.30	0.60	128.29	155.14
0.00	(128.19)	..	0.00	(88.01)	..

EXPERIMENTAL

The pure laboratory chemicals were purified by distillation in pyrex glass vessels and pyrex bottles with special stoppers were used for storing the mixtures. Abbe refractometer with an accuracy of ± 0.0001 was used for measuring n_D^{20} ; density was measured by pycnometer and for these the temperature was maintained within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. Cottrell's method⁷ with slight variations was used for measuring the boiling points.

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 2408.

6. McGraw Hills Book Co., New York, Vol. III, 1926, p. 312.

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 721.